

**CHINA'S BANKING SYSTEM, PROVINCIAL CHINESE BANKING
POLICY**

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Annotation: This article provides information about Chinese Banking system; History of Chinese banking system; Information about Big Four Banks and they activities; structure of China Banking system; benefits of China Banking sytem; comparing Chinese Banks with other biggest banks of the world; why people should invest in Chinese Banking System and economics;

Key words: China banking system, Big Four Banks, Industrial and commercial bank, Construction bank, Agricultural bank, Bank of China.

The People s Republic of China was established in 1-st October 1949 year. But China has a great centuries-old history beginning from 221BC. First similar to bank organizations was created in 10th century during the “Sun” dynasty. Those organizations were able to accept deposits, giving credit loans, exchange currency and transactions between cities, but there were limited people to use such services. In our days Chinese Banking system is one of the most various in world financial market. According to report¹ of the end of 2020 year, total amount of China banking assets rich 49 trillion dollars, which is 2.5 times more than USA banking assets and 3 times more than GDP of China. Most crucial leap of banking system developing was in middle of 19th century, for the period of entering European trade companies. British Oriental Bank was the first bank opened branch in China in 1840 year. Then

¹ https://eng.spdb.com.cn/investor_relations/annual_report/202106/P020210601536091873402.pdf

other banks, participations of Treaty of Nanjing², also started entering in China financial market. At the end of 19th century, there were 9 foreign banks (Deutsch-Asiatische Bank, Yokohama Specie Bank, Banque de l'Indochine, Russo-Asiatic Bank, British Oriental Bank, The Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation and etc.) with 45 branch, those banks were emitting money, accept deposits and giving credit loans. Interesting fact is that time China did not have even one own bank in its own financial market until 1897, when The Imperial Bank of China was established, but main shareholders and management was also foreign investors. After 8 years was found the Central Bank of China named Central State Bank. After overthrowing Qing dynasty at 1911 Bank was renamed to Bank of China. In 1928 year was found new Central Bank of China. People's Bank of China, which was organized during Chinese revolution in 1949, in 1950 was most powerful bank with monopolistic position by displacing and absorbing other banks until 1970. When Deng Xiaoping became a leader of country, banking system was fully reorganized. People's Bank of China's activities were divided between 4 state banks: Industrial and commercial bank, construction bank, agricultural bank and bank of China, while People's Bank of China fully stopped commercial activity and performs only Central Bank obligations. Modern Banking system of China consist of 3 levels and controlling by All China Regulatory Commission.

First level consist of 4 banks: People's China Bank, State Development Bank, Agricultural Development Bank, Export-import Bank. As it was mentioned earlier People's China Bank in our days performs duties of Central Bank. Other 3 banks are responsible for developing in industry sphere, agricultural sphere and external trading.

Second level consist of 4 commercial banks which also called as "Big four banks" and all of them are assets of government:

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https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D0%9D%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%BA%D0%B8%D0%BD%D1%81%D0%BA%D0%B8%D0%B9_%D0%B4%D0%BE%D0%B3%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%BE%D1%80

1. Industrial and commercial bank.

2. Construction bank.

3. Agricultural bank.

4. Bank of China.

Also lease , trust investing and other financial companies are also belong to second level of Chinese Banking system. It is important to mention that until 2001 was prohibited for non-residents having shares of “Big four banks”. Later China s government also decided to allow branch of international banks in country and also opening new commercial banks by residents. Last but not least is agriculture and urban credit cooperatives and post offices. They are to support small and medium businesses in the country. In the new rating of largest assets of world banks 2021 the “Big four banks” of China occupied the top 4 places.

Name	Location	Assets (billion dollars)	
1	Industrial and Commercial Bank of China	China	5114
2	China Construction Bank	China	4315
3	Agricultural Bank of China	China	4173
4	Bank of China	China	3743
5	JPMorgan Chase	USA	3386
6	Mitsubishi Financial Group	UFJ Japan	3268

Name	Location	Assets (billion dollars)	
7	HSBC	UK	2984
8	Bank of America	USA	2820
9	BNP Paribas	France	2763
10	China Development Bank	China	2531

“Big four banks”

1.Industrial and Commercial Bank of China. Largest bank of China and of the world with 5 trillion dollars assets was found in 1984 year and provide services to industrial and energetic companies. In total Bank serve 8.6 millions companies and 680 millions individual clients. In 2006 Bank organized biggest in that time IPO to 21 billion dollars. In addition it was first IPO with double listing in Shanxay and Gongong financial markets. In present time bank has 440.000 employees and 426 branch in 49 countries over the world.

2.China Construction Bank. Second largest Bank in China with 4 trillion dollars assets. Was established in 1954 year and called “People s construction Bank”. As it seems by name Bank specialized to serve construction companies and mortgage. In 2005 Bank also organized 9 billion dollars IPO in Hongkong financial market, whereupon Bank of America bought 9% of CCB shares. In 2013 American Bank fully sold all action of bank

3.Agricultural Bank of China. One of the most senior bank of China founded by Mao Sendum in 1951 year. The number of branch offices shocking – 13.000 in China territory. Total assets more than 4 trillion dollars, IPO in 2010 attracted 19 billion dollars in capital of ABC

4. Bank of China. Last in the top, but not least in economy of China. Eldest Bank in China was found in 1912. In our days total assets of Bank more than 3.7 trillion dollars and has subsidiary in 61 country over the world. Bank of China was first bank in Chinese history which opened branch in USA in 2010 year and offered to Americans banking and investing services in yuan (China national currency). More over Bank was first foreign Bank started activity in Russia in 1993. In 2006 BoC also organized IPO in Hong Kong and Shanghai financial market. Total 13.7 billions dollars was invested in company.

Key interest rate When it comes to key interest rate most Central Banks over the world set single interest rate in all economic spheres in the country. As an example in Uzbekistan it is 15%, in Russia it equal to 7.5%. But China is another story, Central Bank of China (People s Bank of China) sets up 4 key interest rates in different ways of economy.

1. The one-year deposit rate. From 2015 to now it still 1.5% and was created for individuals deposits with 1 year maturity term.

2. The seven-day reverse-repurchase rate (DR 007). It is weekly rate for repo deals between Chinese Banks. Central Bank monthly setting interest rate and regulating banking liquidity. In August 2022 rate was reduced to 2%.

3. The medium-term lending facility. The major interest rate, because all banks accord to this rate before providing credit loans. It rate also actual to commercial banks which going to take loan from Central Bank. In August 2022 it was reduced to 2.75%

4. The loan prime rate. Interest rate for "first class" borrowers. Monthly setting by Central Bank. This interest rate is taking into account to provide mortgage credits.

Incident: In May 2022 thousands people go out to streets in Khenyen with require take back their deposits. The reason of discontent was 5.9 billions dollars stolen by Henan Xincaifu Group Investment Holding .As a result of investigation

all instigators was sentenced to life imprisonment, while all casualties returned money back whereby insurance of deposits.

Dividend income of Chinese Banks : Considering the power of national currency of China yuan no doubt that depositing money in China Banks is profitable for investors. Dividend income of "Big Four" banks of China:

Industrial and Commercial Bank of China	8,78%
China Construction Bank	8,95%
Bank of China	9,52%
Agricultural Bank of China	9,72%

Conclusion To sum up at present time according to develop of Banking System, Industry and Production China is going to be the strongest country in World arena. That's why researching Chinese economics changes and using same methods in own economy would be useful for developing countries economics!

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